

The Influence of Pop-Up Book Media on The Learning Outcomes of Class IV Students on The Subject of Social Sciences, Theme 1, Subtema 3 at SDN 0949109 Raya Pinantar

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to determine the influence of *pop-up book media* on the learning outcomes of class IV students in social studies subjects theme 1 subtheme 3 at SD Negeri 094109 Raya Pinantar. This research is a type of quantitative research using experimental methods with a *one group pretest-posttest design type of research* . The population of this research is all fourth grade students at SD 094109 Raya Pinantar FY 2023/2024, totaling 25 students. The research results at the 0.05 level show that there is an influence of *Pop-Up Book media* on student learning outcomes. After carrying out the validity of the test, a *pretest was carried out* with an average score of 52.48 and the *posttest results* showed that the average score for class IV students was 83.20. By using the N-Gain Test, an average value of 63.27 is obtained, so the results of the N-Gain test are in the medium category, judging from the provisions of the assessment criteria, if $0.70 < n\text{-gain}$, then the assessment criteria are high, and if $0,30 \leq n\text{-gain} \leq 0.70$ then the assessment criteria are medium, and if $n\text{-gain} < 0.30$ then the assessment criteria are low. Thus it can be concluded that there is a significant difference between increasing learning outcomes using *Pop-Up Book media* and increasing learning outcomes without using *Pop-Up Book media*.

INTRODUCTION

Education is an important aspect in forming a quality generation. In Law no. 20 of 2003 article I paragraph I of 2003 concerning the National Education System. stated "Education is a conscious and planned effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble morals and skills needed by themselves, society, nation and state. " Education includes teaching special skills, and also something that cannot be seen but is more profound, namely providing knowledge, consideration and wisdom of educators to students. Teachers and students participate in education in the form of teaching and learning interactions or learning processes. Education at school is said to be successful if educational goals are achieved and student development is seen to increase from day to day.

Based on interview observations conducted by research on June 3 2023 in class I V of SD Negeri 094109 Raya Pinantar Teachers face problems in mastering the class, especially in determining the right learning media so that learning runs well and goals are achieved. In social studies learning, class IV teachers have difficulty implementing creative and innovative social studies learning media. This makes students bored or bored and results in students having difficulty understanding the learning material that has been presented by the teacher. With these problems, there is a need for interactive book media such as *Pop-UP Books* to increase student learning motivation and make learning easier to understand. This type of media has attractive illustration images, is easy to carry and practical to use.

This has a big impact on student learning outcomes which are low and have not yet achieved the Minimum Completeness Criteria (KKM). Where the score for social studies subjects that completed the KKM was 3.6 % , but 64% for those that were not completed . From this data, there are still many students who have not completed their learning.

According to Aqid (Sholeh M, 2019: 139), learning media is anything that can be used to convey messages and stimulate students' learning processes. Media helps build good learning. Media is a tool used by teachers to convey various learning materials, to make it easier for students to understand the material presented by the teacher.

Students in elementary school have different learning characteristics from higher levels of education, elementary school students have an interest in games and visual activities. Therefore, the use of interesting learning media such as *Pop-Up Books* can increase student activity and involvement in the learning process. One of the interactive and interesting learning media is *the Pop-Up Book* . *Pop-Up Book* Media is a book that has folds in it which, when

opened, produce an attractive three-dimensional image. This *Pop-Up Book* media is very practical to use, easy to carry and can increase students' enthusiasm for learning through attractive image visualization.

With the existence of learning media, it is hoped that it can improve student learning outcomes in social studies subjects and overcome learning problems that occur in SD Negeri 094109 Raya Pinantar .

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The thinking framework is a conceptual framework of how theory relates to various factors that have been identified as important problems. Learning outcomes are evidence of learning so that changes occur in an individual. The learning outcomes referred to in this research are learning outcomes in theme 1 subtheme 3 learning 5 with a focus on social studies subjects . Learning outcomes are influenced by several internal and external factors. External factors come from outside the student, while internal factors are factors that come from within the student.

From the problem formulation it can be seen that there is one independent variable which is expressed as (X) and one dependent variable which is expressed as (Y). The independent variable is *the Pop-Up Book* media (X), and the dependent variable is student learning outcomes (Y), thus the *Pop-Up Book media* related to the learning outcomes of class I V students at SD Negeri 094109 Raya Pinantar.

RESEARCH METHODS

The research used in this research uses a quantitative approach. With a *pre-Experimental Design type*. Where the researcher used a *One-group Pretest-Posttest Design*. In research, the results of the treatment will be known more accurately because you can compare the conditions before the treatment was given. (Sugiyono: 2018).

Figure 1 One-Group Pretest-Posttest Design

Information:

O₁ = pretest score

O₂ = posttest score

X = treatment given

The population in this study were all students in class IV of SD Negeri 094109 Raya Pinantar with a total of 25 students. This research uses a test instrument in the form of multiple choices with the aim of measuring learning outcomes. Before it is used for data collection, the data testing stage uses validity testing, reliability testing, difficulty level testing, and differentiating data testing. In data analysis, the T Test and N-Gain Test Hypothesis tests were used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

The location of the school used as the research site is SD Negeri 094109 Raya Pinantar, which is located at JL. Karmen Saragih No.15, Pematang Raya, Raya District, Simalungun Regency. The current principal is Mr. Jadesrin Purba, S.Pd., M.Pd. This school is accredited B (good). There are 12 teachers and education personnel and 1,62 students.

This research was conducted in October 14 - October 24 2023. In this research, researchers used a pre-experimental type of research using a one group pretest-posttest design. In the research process, the researcher first gave an initial test (pretest) to students before being given treatment using learning using media *Pop-Up Book* and provide a final test (posttest) after being given

treatment. This research was conducted after testing the instrument. The subjects of this research were 25 students in class I V of elementary school for the 2023/2024 academic year , consisting of 12 male students and 13 female students. The time allocation used for each meeting is 2 x 35 minutes.

Test instrument

1. Validity test

This test is carried out by calculating r using the Pearson product moment formula and then comparing the r table . If the calculated $r > r$ table at a significance level of 0.05 then the question is valid for use in measuring this variable, conversely if the $r < r$ table then the question tool is invalid and not suitable for use. There are 25 questions that have valid marks , while there are 5 questions that are invalid .

2. Reliability Test

The question reliability test aims to see the accuracy of the tool in assessing what it assesses. In this case, observe how each question item is determined in assessing or testing students' abilities and knowledge. To test reliability using Cronbach Alpha, namely if the Cronbach Alpha value is > 0.60 then the data is declared reliable. And if the Cronbach Alpha value is < 0.60 then the data is declared unreliable. Based on the results of reliability tests using SPSS 26 *Cronbach Alpha* has a value of 0.924. This shows that question items number 1-30 used in the *pretest* and *posttest questions* have very high reliability values.

3. Test Difficulty Level

The difficulty level test is carried out to see the level of difficulty of each question that has been distributed and determine whether the question is too easy or too difficult. Of the 30 questions tested, 6 questions were classified as easy (8,18,24,27,28,30), 19 questions were classified as medium (1,2,3,4,5,7,11,13,14,15,16,17,19,21,22,23,25,26,29) and 5 questions in the like r category (6,9,10,12,20).

4. Discriminating Power Test

This test is carried out to find out whether the question items have a classification of very bad, bad, fair, good or very good . Based on the processing results of the differentiating power test, there were 4 questions in the poor category, 23 good, and 3 questions in the very good category.

Data analysis

1. N-Gain Test

N-Gain test aims to see the effectiveness of the learning media used, namely the *Pop-Up Book media*. The *N-Gain* test results were carried out using SPSS version 26 with the following data:

Table 1 N-Gain Test

No	Name	Mark		Post-Pre	Ideal Score (100-Pre)	N-Gain Score	N-Gain Score (%)
		Pre test	Post test				
1	Amora Anastasya Pardede	52	80	28	48	0.58	58.33
2	Andryan Edward Purba	72	96	20	24	0.83	83.33
3	Aura Apriani Saragih	52	80	28	48	0.58	58.33
4	Ben Gracello Damanik	40	80	40	60	0.67	66.67
5	Caroline Elizabeth Sidauruk	40	84	44	60	0.73	73.33
6	Dina Maharani Saragih	48	84	36	52	0.69	69.23
7	Dini Ardika Purba	60	80	20	40	0.50	50.00
8	El Yada Wiliam Sinurat	36	76	40	64	0.63	62.50
9	Fiona Cristabel Purba	60	92	32	40	0.80	80.00
10	Immanuel Rado Hutabarat	56	84	28	44	0.64	63.64
11	Jorell Khenza Sitanggang	36	88	52	64	0.81	81.25
12	Joy Enjelina Silalahi	56	76	20	44	0.45	45.45
13	Karin Dwi Alexa Damanik	68	80	12	32	0.38	37.50
14	Lorenz Alvaro Purba	64	84	20	36	0.56	55.56
15	Michael Christian Sumbayak	76	84	8	24	0.33	33.33
16	Naura Firna Sinaga	44	80	36	56	0.64	64.29
17	Oktavia Nursaidah Simarmata	60	76	16	40	0.40	40.00
18	Reananda Pratama Sinaga	36	80	44	64	0.69	68.75
19	Reinanda Anggian Sinaga	52	92	40	48	0.83	83.33
20	Rifaldo Purba	36	88	52	64	0.81	81.25
21	Teresa Adinda Bintang Saragih	48	84	36	52	0.69	69.23
22	Tri Argado Damanik	64	92	28	36	0.78	77.78
23	Yesi Debora Sinaga	52	84	32	48	0.67	66.67
24	Yola Anggia Purba	56	84	28	44	0.64	63.64
25	Yose Castelo Purba	48	72	24	52	0.46	46.15
Mean		52.48	83.20	30.72	47.52	0.63	63.27

The *N-gain* test value data was 63.27 with a medium classification and quite effective category. So, it can be concluded that this *Pop-Up Book Media* is quite effective in application.

2. Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing was carried out to determine the positive and significant influence between *Pop-Up Book* media and student learning outcomes. Hypothesis testing using a paired simple t test with the help of IBM SPSS 26 with the following results:

		Paired Differences					Q	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Pretest - Posttest	-30.560	11.598	2.320	-35.347	-25.773	-13.175	24	.000

To determine the price of ttable, the researcher used the t distribution with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ and $db = N - 1 = 30 - 1 = 29$, so we obtained $t_{0.05} = 1.699$. After obtaining $t_{count} = 32.669$ and $t_{table} = 1.699$, it can be seen that $t_{count} > t_{table}$ or $32.669 > 1.699$. So it can be concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This explanation shows that there is an influence of the image media type learning model on student learning outcomes for theme 1 subtheme 3 animal growth class III SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar.

Discussion

This research was conducted to determine the influence of *Pop-Up media Book* on learning outcomes for class I V on theme 1 subtheme 3 at SD Negeri 094109 Raya Pinantar . Researchers chose this *pop-up book media* because it is very practical to use, easy to carry and can increase students' enthusiasm for learning through attractive image visualization. The unique thing about *Pop-Up Books* is that the pages contain elements that can jump or appear when the book is opened. This media also emphasizes student activity in discovering the concepts being studied and educators only act as facilitators. In this research, researchers used a pre-experimental type of research using a one group pretest-posttest design.

In the research process, the researcher first gave an initial test (pretest) to students before being given treatment using learning using Pop-Up Book media and gave a final test (posttest) after being given treatment. The student's highest score on the pretest was 68 and the lowest score was 36 . Where 25 students are

still below the KKM, this is because students do not fully understand the material, are less active when learning, and learning is still monotonous. After being given a pretest, the researcher taught using pop-up book media .

Learning using pop-up book media was carried out in 2 meetings. When learning takes place, students look active and enthusiastic about learning. After 2 meetings, the researcher gave a final test (posttest) to see the final results. The average posttest score was 83 , where the highest score was 96 and the lowest score was 72 . Based on the results of data analysis and hypothesis testing, the average pretest score is 52 and the average posttest score is 83. Based on the average *posttest results* , learning using *pop-up book media* has better learning outcomes. Based on the *Paired Sample T Test* test table, it is known that the significance value (2-tailed) is 0.000. Then $0.000 < 0.05$. This can be concluded to mean that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which means that there is an influence of *pop-up book media* on the learning outcomes of class IV students in social studies subject theme 1 subtheme 3 at SD Negeri 094109 Raya Pinantar.

After conducting research, it was seen that there were changes experienced by students, from not understanding to understanding, from being less active to being active, and there was an increase in grades. This is because the learning media is interesting and focuses on students so that students are interested in participating in learning .

CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

Based on the results of research conducted by researchers, the following conclusions can be drawn:

Based on the results of the research and discussion that has been carried out, it can be concluded that student learning outcomes obtained an average pretest score of 52.64, whereas after being given treatment using Pop-Up Book media, an average posttest score of 83.20 was obtained and there was a significant influence from the use of Pop-Up Book media. on student learning outcomes. It is known that the significance value (2-tailed) is 0.000. Then $0.000 < 0.05$. This can be concluded to mean that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which means that there is an influence of the Pop-Up Book media on the learning outcomes of class IV students in social studies subject theme 1 subtheme 3 at SD Negeri 094109 Raya Pinantar.

Recommendations

Based on the research that has been carried out, as recommendation material by considering findings in the field and theoretically, the author's suggestions are:

1. For Schools

Pop-Up Book Media will become one of the learning media applied to improve student learning outcomes.

2. For Teachers

It is hoped that a teacher can choose the right learning media when carrying out learning. The media chosen must be able to attract students' attention, have the ability to motivate students to participate more actively in teaching and learning activities.

3. For Other Researchers

So that this research can be useful for readers, it is hoped that it can become a reference for requirements for preparing further research.

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